

CEMENT FACTORY MACHINES OPERATING AT 120 HZ THERMAL ENERGY GENERATIONS USING THREE-PHASE SQUIRREL CAGE MACHINES

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Abstract: *Cement factory machines operating at 120 Hz thermal energy generations using three-phase squirrel cage machines is presented. A cement is an adhesive chemical substances used for construction that set, hardens and adheres to other materials to bind them together. Cement manufacturing is a complex process that begins with mining and then grinding raw materials that include limestone and clay which is then heated to a sintering temperature as high as 1450 °C in a cement kiln. It is a finely ground powders that, when mixed with water it set and hardened mass. Thermal energy is the energy that comes from hot temperature of matters. Heat is the flow of thermal energy and three types of thermal energy are conduction, radiation and convection. Convection is a cyclical process that only occurs in fluids. Squirrel cage machines are machine whose rotor is cylindrical mounted on the shaft of copper or aluminum bars. Due to its ruggedness in construction and low maintenance found applications in industrial drives, mills, turning machines, pump, fan and blowers. The inadequate generating capacity, frequent grids collapses, and power outages in developing countries has made the call for distributed generation imperative. Electromagnetic three-phase squirrel cage machine of electrical and mechanical design energy generation depend on the heat transfer within the various parts of the three-phase squirrel cage machine. The thermal effect in three-phase squirrel cage machine is complex, non-linear, and difficult and the behavior is differently from other conventional machines electromagnetically. The rotor speed shows that the speed of the machine drops at time equals 0.5s due to load application, the torque increases from 0Nm to 31Nm which is the value of the mechanical load torque. The transient period of the machine dies down about 0.15s after start-up and the magnitude of the steady state value of the stator phase currents increases as the load is applied at time equals 0.5s. The investigation finds application where critical temperature of the three-phase squirrel cage machine parts during and after machine load ability is imperative. The thermal properties of the materials used in designing of the three-phase squirrel cage machines and the constant heat transfer coefficients parameters were determined from developed thermal model information. The electrical and mechanical thermal model development in addition to computer simulation show that the cement factory electrical thermal effect energy generation to operate from 120 Hz using three-phase squirrel cage machines is very effective for the smooth plant operation and recommended for cement factories and energy generating industries.*

Keywords: *thermal, factory, three-phase squirrel cage, heat, coefficient Electromagnetic, torque and temperature.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Cement factory machines operating at 120 Hz thermal energy generations using three phase squirrel cage machines is presented. A cement is an adhesive chemical substances used for construction that set, hardens and adheres to other materials to bind them together. Cement manufacturing is a complex process that begins with mining and then grinding raw materials that include limestone and clay which is then heated to a sintering temperature as high as 1450 °C in a cement kiln. It is a finely ground powders that, when mixed with water it set and hardened mass. Thermal energy is the energy that comes from hot temperature of matters. Heat is the flow of thermal energy and three types of thermal energy are conduction, radiation and convection. Convection is a cyclical process that only occurs in fluids. Squirrel cage induction machines are widely used in industrial and domestic. The rotor is cylindrical mounted on the shaft that contains copper or aluminum bars. Due to its ruggedness in construction and low maintenance found applications in industrial drives, mills, turning machines, pump, fan and blowers. The inadequate generating capacity, frequent grids collapses, and power outages in developing countries has made the call for distributed generation imperative [1, 4]. Electricity could be extended to remote villages that are not connected to the grid. The dynamic behavior of three phase squirrel cage machine has received a considerable attention in most researched works [4, 5, 6]. The computer simulation of symmetrical three phase squirrel cage machine was carried out [4, 5]. Electromagnetic for three-phase squirrel cage machine of Electrical and mechanical design for energy generation depend on the heat transfer within the various parts of the three phase squirrel cage machine. The thermal effect in three-phase squirrel cage machine is complex, non-linear and difficult. The behavior is differently from other conventional machines electromagnetically. The dynamic and thermal modeling of three-phase squirrel cage machine with saturation and skin-effect was investigated [2, 7]. The digital computer simulation of three phase squirrel cage machine in dynamic systems was discussed [2, 6]. Effort was made to investigate the effect of coupling the Electrical and Thermal models of the machine with the view of determining the overall three phase squirrel cage machine behaviors in dynamic state.

2.0 Three-Phase Squirrel Cage Machine Electrical Model

Differential equations of non-linear which describe the dynamic performance of an ideal symmetrical three phase squirrel cage machine in an arbitrary reference frame operating cement factory from 120 Hz was derived from the d-q equivalent circuits of figure 1 as in [2, 4]. Figure1a shows cement factory three-phase squirrel cage machines q-axis model and figure1b shows cement factory three-phase squirrel cage machines d-axis model. Thermal networks and an equivalent of Electrical networks are applied by [2, 7] while in [6, 8] the Finite Element Method of analysis was used. The mechanical and electrical models of the machine development thermal models fail because the method used a weak

coupled modeling in the analysis of three-phase squirrel cage machine. Analysis method has been noted but computationally expensive in software development and hardware implementation. Finite-Element Method was used in the analysis [2, 7, 10].

Type equation here.

$$\begin{pmatrix} V_{qs} \\ V_{ds} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (R_s + L_s P) & \omega L_s & L_m P & \omega L_m \\ -\omega L_s & (R_s + L_s P) & -\omega L_m & L_m P \\ L_m P & (\omega - \omega_r) L_m & (R_r + L_r P) & (\omega - \omega) L_m \\ -(\omega - \omega_r) L_m & L_m P & -(\omega - \omega_r) L_r & (R_r + L_r P) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_{qs} \\ i_{ds} \\ i_{qr} \\ i_{dr} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where,

$$L_s = L_{ls} + L_m \quad (2)$$

$$L_r = L_{lr} + L_m \quad (3)$$

$$P = \frac{d}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Figure1a: Cement Factory Three-phase Squirrel Cage Machines q-axis model

Figure1b: Cement Factory Three-phase Squirrel Cage Machines d-axis model

$$\begin{pmatrix} V_{qs} \\ V_{ds} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (R_s + L_s P) & \omega_r L_s & L_m P & \omega_r L_m \\ -\omega_r L_s & (R_s + L_s P) & -\omega_r L_m & L_m P \\ L_m P & 0 & (R_r + L_r P) & 0 \\ 0 & L_m P & 0 & (R_r + L_r P) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i_{qs} \\ i_{ds} \\ i_{qr} \\ i_{dr} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Transforming (1) to d-q axis fixed on the rotor we have equation (5) and is represented in a state variable form.

$$P[i] = -[L]^{-1} ([R] + \omega_r [G]) [i] + [L]^{-1} [V] \quad (6)$$

Where

$$[V] = [V_{qs} \quad V_{ds} \quad 0 \quad 0] \quad (7)$$

$$[R] = \text{diag} (R_s \quad R_s \quad R_r \quad R_r) \quad (8)$$

$$[L] = \begin{pmatrix} L_s & 0 & L_m & 0 \\ 0 & L_s & 0 & L_m \\ L_m & 0 & L_r & 0 \\ 0 & L_m & 0 & L_r \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$[G] = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & L_s & 0 & L_m \\ L_s & 0 & L_m & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$[i] = [i_{qs} \quad i_{ds} \quad i_{qr} \quad i_{dr}] \quad (11)$$

Torque equation for electromagnetic squirrel cage machine

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} P L_m (i_{qs} i_{dr} - i_{ds} i_{qr}) \quad (12)$$

Where P = number of pole

The three phase squirrel cage machine may be consider as Sinusoidal under balance condition and express as

$$V_{as} = \sqrt{2V} \cos \omega_b t \quad (13)$$

$$V_{bs} = \sqrt{2V} \cos \left(\omega_b t - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \quad (14)$$

$$V_{cs} = \sqrt{2V} \cos \left(\omega_b t + \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) \quad (15)$$

The three phase squirrel cage machine stator voltage are related to the d-q machine reference frame thus,

$$\begin{pmatrix} V_{qs} \\ V_{ds} \end{pmatrix} = [C_1] \begin{pmatrix} V_{cs} \\ V_{cs} \\ V_{cs} \end{pmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Where,

$$[C_1] = \frac{2}{3} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \emptyset & \cos \emptyset \left(\emptyset - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) & \cos \emptyset \left(\emptyset - \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) \\ \sin \emptyset & \sin \emptyset \left(\emptyset - \frac{2\pi}{3} \right) & \sin \emptyset \left(\emptyset - \frac{4\pi}{3} \right) \end{pmatrix} \quad (17)$$

This also apply to stator phase current related to d-q axis current as

$$\begin{pmatrix} i_{as} \\ i_{as} \\ i_{as} \end{pmatrix} = [C]^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} i_{as} \\ i_{as} \\ i_{as} \end{pmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$[C_1]^{-1} = \frac{2}{3} \begin{pmatrix} \cos\phi & \sin\phi \\ \cos\phi \left(\phi - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) & \sin\phi \left(\phi - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ \cos\phi \left(\phi - \frac{4\pi}{3}\right) & \sin\phi \left(\phi - \frac{4\pi}{3}\right) \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

3.0 Three-Phase Squirrel Cage Machine Mechanical Model

The three-phase squirrel cage machine mechanical model comprises the equations of motion for the three-phase squirrel cage machine driven load in second order differential equation [2, 7] three-phase squirrel cage machine mechanical model schematic as shown in figure 2.

$$J_m \frac{d^2\theta_m}{dt^2} = T_c - T_L \quad (20)$$

Decomposing equation (55) into two first order differential equation gives,

$$P\theta_m = \omega_m \quad (21)$$

$$J_m (P \omega_m) = T_c - T_L \quad (22)$$

Figure 2: Three-phase squirrel cage machine mechanical model schematic.

$$P \omega_m = \frac{1}{J_m} (T_c - T_L) \quad (23)$$

But

$$\omega_r = \omega_m P \quad (24)$$

$$\theta_r = \theta_m P \quad (25)$$

Three phase squirrel-cage machine thermal model, the thermal model for the three phase squirrel-cage machine is developed according to the principles [5, 7] the stator iron and the Frame. The values of the thermal resistances and capacitances were calculated according to the principles reported by

[4, 5]. Table 2 shows the computed values. The developed electrical-thermal model gives rise to a set of differential equations which describe both the thermal and electromechanical behaviors of the machine under dynamic conditions. MATLAB m-files were developed in other to determine the average temperature rise in the various parts of the machine as well as losses in the machine [3, 9]. The MATLAB m-files use the Runge-Kutta numerical method [1, 6] to solve the state variable.

4.0 Three Phase Squirrel-Cage Machine Electrical and Thermal Models Coupling

The interaction of the electrical, mechanical and thermal models is realized by coupling the electrical model with the thermal model as shown in Figure 1. The Electrical model is expected to determine the losses dissipated in the various parts of the rotor. The stator and rotor equivalent resistances are varied as functions of their average temperatures. The thermal model is derived by considering the power losses and rate of temperature rise in various parts of the motor. The model thermal resistances and capacitances are evaluated using the motor construction data. The input to the thermal model is calculated from the electrical model. The mechanical model comprises of the equations of motion of the motor and driven load. By using the mechanical model, motor speed can be measured or calculated during motor operation. The mechanical model, therefore presents the motor speed as an input to the electrical model. Therefore, by coupling the electrical and thermal models, the power losses of the thermal model are given by the electrical model while the temperatures in the equivalent resistances used in the electrical model are corrected by the thermal model. The two models are calculated in parallel. It is imperative to state that before each calculation step of temperatures, the heat loss inputs have to be determined. The strategy for evaluating these losses for every need of the thermal model takes enormous computer time since the thermal time constants of the motor are higher than the electrical ones. In order to reduce the simulation time as well as the transient time, the calculated thermal time constants of the motor are further reduced by a factor of 100. The mathematical representation of the coupled system in state variable form is,

$$\frac{d\theta_1}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_1} \left(P_1 - \frac{1}{R_{1a}} (\theta_1 - \theta_a) - \frac{1}{R_{12}} (\theta_1 - \theta_2) - \frac{1}{R_{13}} (\theta_1 - \theta_3) \right) \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{d\theta_2}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_2} \left(P_2 - \frac{1}{R_{24}} (\theta_2 - \theta_4) - \frac{1}{R_{21}} (\theta_2 - \theta_1) \right) \quad (27)$$

$$\left(\frac{d\theta_3}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_3} \left(P_3 - \frac{1}{R_{31}} (\theta_3 - \theta_1) - \frac{1}{R_{34}} (\theta_3 - \theta_4) \right) \right) \quad (28)$$

$$\left(\frac{d\theta_4}{dt} = \frac{1}{C_4} P_4 - \frac{1}{R_4} (\theta_{4b} - \theta_b) - \frac{1}{R_{42}} (\theta_4 - \theta_2) - \frac{1}{R_{43}} (\theta_4 - \theta_3) \right) \quad (29)$$

Where

$P_1 - P_2$ = heat losses, $\theta_1 - \theta_2$ = Rise in temperature, $R_{12} - R_{13}$ = Thermal resistance. And $C_1 - C_4$ = Thermal capacitance.

5.0 Laboratory Investigation on cement factory machines operating at 120 Hz thermal energy generations using three-phase squirrel cage machines

A laboratory experiment was carried out in the standard research UNIPOINT laboratory to investigate the cement factory machines operating at 120 Hz thermal energy generations using three-phase squirrel cage machines.

Materials, Instruments and Components: The materials, instruments and components used are as follows: Synchronous machine, Three phase Squirrel cage machine, Resistance Module, Three-Phase Wattmeter Module, Power Supply Module (0-220/415V three phase, 220Vdc), AC Metering Module (2.5/2.5/2.5A), AC Metering Module (250/250V), Hand Tachometer, Connection Leads, Timing Belt. Using the instrument, materials and components, the circuit was as shown in figure 3a. The stator of the synchronous motor was connected to power supply 415V three phase output, terminals 1, 2, and 3. The rotor of the synchronous motor was connected to power supply 220Vdc output, terminals 8 and N. The stator of the three phase squirrel cage machine was connected through the wattmeter, to the variable power supply 41V three phase output of the, terminals 4, 5, and 6. The rotor windings were terminated at the delta connected resistance load 'R_L'. The synchronous machine was couple to the three phase squirrel cage machine rotor frequency converter with the timing belt. The load resistance switches were adjusted to their open positions. The field control rheostat of the synchronous machine was set at its full anti clockwise position for maximum resistance. The synchronous machine switch S, was set to the open position. The power supply was turn "ON" and, the machine started running. The synchronous machine switch 'S' was close. The power supply voltage E₁ = 415Vac. was measured and recorded. It was observed that E₂ was zero; it means that the rotor was revolving in the same direction as the magnetic field of the stator. Then, power supply was Turn "OFF" and interchange of the two of the leads to the stator was made. DC excitation of the synchronous machine was adjusted so that current 'I₃' is at its minimum value. The E₂, I₂, W₁, and W₂ was measured and recorded as: E₂ = 208Vac, I₂ = 0Aac, I₂ = 0.65Aac, W₁ = -20W, W₂ = 92W.

Figure3a: Cement Factory Machines Laboratory Research using Three-Phase Squirrel Cage Machines (*delta connected resistance load*) [UNIPOINT LABORATORY]

Three-phase resistance loading was gradually increased by adjusting each resistance section to 240 ohms and $E_2, I_2, I_1, W_1,$ and W_2 was Measure and record as: $E_2 = 175V_{ac}, I_2 = 1.25A_{ac}, I_1 = 1.0 A_{ac}, W_1 = 63W, W_2 = 198W$. The load was removed by opening the resistance switches. The voltage was return to zero and the power supply was turn “OFF”. The real power delivered to the stator and the real power delivered to the delta connected load was calculate thus: *power to stator* $W_1 + W_2 = 643 + 198 = 261 W$ and *power to load* $E_2 \times I_2 \times 1.73 = 175 \times 1.25 \times 1.73 = 218.75 \times 1.73 = 378 W$.

Three phase squirrel cage machine was replace with the delta connected resistance load with the delta (wye) connected machine load as shown in Figure 3b. The power supply was turn “ON” and adjust until $E_1 = 415V_{ac}$.

The squirrel cage machine speed was Measure and record as: $I_1, I_2, E_2, W_1,$ and W_2 . Thus, $E_2 = 196V_{ac}, I_2 = 0.35 A_{ac}, I_1 = 0.8 A_{ac}, W_1 = -28 W, W_2 = 128 W, r/min = 3570$. The voltage was returned to zero and the power supply was turned “OFF”. The results of the tests and the parameters of the machine used are shown in Table 1.

Figure3b: Cement Factory Machines Laboratory Research using Three-Phase Squirrel Cage Machines (replace with the delta connected resistance load with the delta (wye) connected machine load) [UNIPOINT LABORATORY]

Table 1: Machine parameter

Rated frequency	50Hz
Rated voltage (Delta Connection)	180V
Rated current	18.5A
Number of poles	4
Mechanical load torque	31Nm
Rated power	4.8KW
Rotor resistance	0.5253Ω
Stator resistance	0.601364Ω
Stator leakage inductance	1.870057mH
Rotor leakage inductance	5.726896mH
Magnetizing inductance	0.4804792H
Estimated rotor inertia Moment	0.0303821kg m ²

Source: [2, 7]

Table 2: Resistances and Capacitances Thermal Calculated Values

Thermal Capacitance s	Values[J/K]	Thermal resistances	Values[K/W]
C1	22897.175	R _{1a}	0.0416
C2	963.308	R _{4b}	0.015
C3	3831.132	R ₁₂ R ₂₄	10.749 X 10 ⁻³ 0.16022
C4	1006	R ₁₃ R ₃₄	0.092 0.0948

Table3: Result of Experimental on Cement Factory Machines Operating At 120 Hz Thermal Energy Generations Using Three-Phase Squirrel Cage Machines.

I₂ (AMPS)	E₁ (VOLTS)	I₁ (Amp)	POWER (VA)	W₁	W₂	POWER (Watts)	PF
0	415	0.80	288	-47	114	67	0.23
0.1	415	0.62	235	-37	93	56	0.25
0.2	415	0.46	166	-17	70	53	0.32
0.3	415	0.24	86.4	10	40	50	0.58
0.4	415	0.14	50.4	25	25	50	0.99
0.5	415	0.20	72.0	40	10	50	0.70
0.6	415	0.35	126	66	-12	54	0.43
0.7	415	0.52	187	80	-24	56	0.30
0.8	415	0.68	245	100	-35	65	0.27

Figure 4: Stator phase currents versus time function at run-up condition

Figure 5: Graph of axis current ID and IQ against time at run up condition

Figure 6: Graph of axes voltages VD and VQ against Time.

Figure 7: Heat losses in stator winding and rotor iron and bar versus time function

Figure 8: Graph of Heat losses in statoriron and frame versus time function

Figure 9: Graph of Coupled Models Temperatures

Figure 10: Graph of stator and rotor resistances versus time function

Figure 11: Graph of Torque versus Time.

Figure 12: Graph of Copper losses Against Time.

The stator of the squirrel cage machine connected to the 60Hz power supply and the rotor driven at 1800r/min by the synchronous machine. The direction of rotation is opposite to that of the revolving magnetic field created by the stator windings and consequently, the frequency of the rotor output voltage is 120Hz. This is because the electrical power delivered by a rotary frequency converter comes from two sources.

- ❖ The electrical power supply to which the stator windings are connected, and
- ❖ The mechanical power delivered to rotating rotor shaft.

Where the output frequency is doubled, the mechanical power and the electrical power to the stator are equal, and then the rotary frequency converter delivers twice as much electric power to its load as its stator receives. The difference comes from the source of mechanical power driving factor. This type of rotary frequency converters is employed in industry to generate the higher frequencies necessary to drive small, high-speed squirrel cage machines.

Figure 4: Stator phase currents versus time function at run-up condition, figure 5: Graph of axis current ID and IQ against time at run up condition, figure 6: Graph of axes voltages VD and VQ against Time, figure 7: Heat losses in stator winding and rotor iron and bar versus time function, figure 8: Graph of Heat losses in stator iron and frame versus time function, figure 9: Graph of

Coupled Models Temperatures, figure 10: Graph of stator and rotor resistances versus time function, figure 11: Graph of Torque versus Time, figure 12: Graph of Copper losses Against Time. The time function of the speed, electromagnetic torque, stator phase currents and resistance is depicted in figure 4, figure 7 show the heat losses associated with the component parts of the squirrel cage machine. The rotor speed shows that the speed of the machine drops at time equals 0.5s due to load application. But at the instant of the load application, the torque increases from 0Nm to 31Nm which is the value of the mechanical load torque as the electromagnetic-time curve. The transient period of the machine dies down about 0.15s after start-up. The magnitude of the steady state value of the stator phase currents increases as the load is applied at time equals 0.5s. That is, both the stator and rotor resistances have an initial peak rise but remain constant after the application of load. The great amount of heat losses occur at the rotor iron and rotor bar of the machine. The stator iron and frame have the least heat losses, figure: 9 shows the temperature rise of the various parts of the machine. The rotor iron and rotor bar respond sharply to heat compared to other parts of the machine with a peak temperature of about 125°C.

6.0 CONCLUSION

The electrical and mechanical thermal interactions in a three-phase squirrel cage machines have been presented in this paper by coupling an electrical model with a thermal model. A d-q axis model used to predict the electrical characteristics of the machine with temperature effect and heat losses. The thermal properties of the materials used in designing of the three-phase squirrel cage machines and the constant heat transfer coefficients parameters were determined from developed thermal model information. The analysis presented in this paper is useful when the variable load conditions as in the case of energy generation. The temperature increase of three-phase squirrel cage machines parts was as a result of predicted load variations. Electrical-thermal coupled of three-phase squirrel cage machine simple method of modeling and mechanical model is presented in this paper. The electrical and mechanical thermal model development in addition to computer simulation show that the cement factory electrical thermal effect for energy generation to operate from 120 Hz using three-phase squirrel cage machines is very effective for the smooth plant operation and recommended industries and cement factories.

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